

The central-divisor exception set for three-prime layers

Eric Fodge

June 4, 2026

Abstract

For a positive integer n let $g(n)$ be the largest divisor of n not exceeding \sqrt{n} (OEIS A033676), let $G_a = \{n : g(n) = a\}$, and let $X_a = \{m \text{ composite} : a \leq m \leq a^2, g(am) = a\}$ be the central-divisor exception set (rows of OEIS A163925, sizes A163926). Companion notes determine $|X_a|$ for prime, prime power, and squarefree two-prime layers, where in each case $|X_a| \asymp a^2/(\beta(a) \log^2 a)$ with $\beta(a) = \min\{d^-(d)d^-(e) : d, e \mid a, de > a\}$ the band invariant. Here we settle the first three-prime case. For squarefree $a = pqr$ with $p < q < r$ we prove

$$|X_{pqr}| \asymp \frac{a^2}{\beta_3(a) \log^2 a}, \quad \beta_3(a) = \min(qr, p^2r, p^2q^2),$$

in fixed logarithmic shape $\log q / \log p \rightarrow \lambda$, $\log r / \log p \rightarrow \mu$, away from the boundary surfaces $\lambda = 2$, $\mu = \lambda + 2$, $\mu = 2\lambda$. The three regimes give cloud scales p^2qr , q^2r , and r^2 . The upper bound is the divisor-pair machinery of the companion note; the lower bounds come from three explicit survivor families, one per regime, each shown to lie in X_a by an explicit divisor check: am is a product of five distinct primes, and every divisor of am is either at most a or exceeds \sqrt{am} . The result confirms, for $\omega(a) = 3$, that the single extremal divisor pair controls the order of the count, and we state the general squarefree conjecture $|X_a| \asymp a^2/(\beta(a) \log^2 a)$ with numerical evidence through $\omega(a) = 4$.

1 Introduction

For $n \geq 1$ let $g(n) = \max\{d : d \mid n, d \leq \sqrt{n}\}$ (OEIS A033676) and $G_a = \{n : g(n) = a\}$. Writing $n = am$,

$$am \in G_a \iff am \text{ has no divisor in } (a, \sqrt{am}], \quad (1)$$

and the composite multipliers form the finite exception set

$$X_a = \{m \text{ composite} : a \leq m \leq a^2, am \in G_a\}, \quad (2)$$

the rows of OEIS A163925, with sizes A163926. The companion notes [1, 2, 3] evaluate $|X_a|$ by factorization type:

$$|X_a| \sim \frac{1}{2} a^2 / \log^2 a \quad (a \text{ prime}), \quad (3)$$

$$|X_{p^k}| \asymp_k a^{1+1/k} / \log^2 a \quad (a = p^k, p \geq 3), \quad (4)$$

$$|X_{pq}| \asymp a^2 / (\beta(a) \log^2 a), \quad \beta(pq) = \min(q, p^2) \quad (a = pq, p < q). \quad (5)$$

In all three the order is $a^2/(\beta(a) \log^2 a)$, where

$$\beta(a) = \min\{d^-(d)d^-(e) : d, e \mid a, de > a\} \quad (6)$$

is the band invariant of [3]: here $d^-(d)$ is the largest divisor of a strictly less than d , the predecessor of d in the divisor lattice. The general note [3] proves the *ceiling law*: writing $C_a(x) = \min\{d \mid a : dx > a\}$, every $m \in X_a$ with $q = P^-(m)$ (smallest prime factor) and $n = m/q$ satisfies

$$C_a(q) C_a(n) > a, \quad (7)$$

from which the *band law* $m \leq a^2/\beta(a)$ and a *divisor-pair majorant* follow. For $\omega(a) \geq 3$ that note leaves the exact count open. This paper closes the first such case, $\omega(a) = 3$.

Result. Let $a = pqr$, $p < q < r$ prime, and fix the logarithmic shape

$$\frac{\log q}{\log p} \rightarrow \lambda, \quad \frac{\log r}{\log p} \rightarrow \mu, \quad 1 < \lambda < \mu, \quad (8)$$

so $q = p^{\lambda+o(1)}$, $r = p^{\mu+o(1)}$, $a = p^{1+\lambda+\mu+o(1)}$.

Theorem 1. With $a = pqr$ in fixed shape (8), away from the boundary surfaces $\lambda = 2$, $\mu = \lambda + 2$, $\mu = 2\lambda$,

$$|X_{pqr}| \asymp \frac{a^2}{\beta_3(a) \log^2 a}, \quad \beta_3(a) = \min(qr, p^2r, p^2q^2),$$

with implied constants depending only on λ, μ . Equivalently

$$|X_{pqr}| \asymp \begin{cases} p^2qr/\log^2 a, & \lambda < 2, \mu < \lambda + 2 \quad (\beta_3 = qr), \\ q^2r/\log^2 a, & \lambda > 2, \mu < 2\lambda \quad (\beta_3 = p^2r), \\ r^2/\log^2 a, & \mu > \max(\lambda + 2, 2\lambda) \quad (\beta_3 = p^2q^2). \end{cases}$$

The denominator $\beta_3(a) = \beta(pqr)$ is the band invariant (6) specialized to three primes (Proposition 2); the theorem says it controls not just the band $\max X_a \leq a^2/\beta(a)$ but the order of the entire count. Section 2 computes β_3 and classifies the regimes; Section 3 gives the upper bound from [3]; Section 4 proves the three survivor families and assembles the theorem; Section 5 states the general squarefree conjecture.

2 The three-prime band invariant

Proposition 2. For $a = pqr$ with $p < q < r$ prime, $\beta(a) = \min(qr, p^2r, p^2q^2)$.

Proof. The divisors of a are $1, p, q, r, pq, pr, qr, pqr$. We must minimize $d^-(d) d^-(e)$ over the ordered pairs (d, e) of divisors with $de > a$; there are 16 unordered admissible pairs (28 ordered, counting each off-diagonal pair twice). The tables below list the unordered pairs. The predecessor function depends on the position of r relative to pq , giving two orderings.

Ordering I ($r < pq$): $1 < p < q < r < pq < pr < qr < pqr$, with

$$d^-(p) = 1, \quad d^-(q) = p, \quad d^-(r) = q, \quad d^-(pq) = r, \quad d^-(pr) = pq, \quad d^-(qr) = pr, \quad d^-(pqr) = qr.$$

The 16 admissible unordered pairs $\{d, e\}$ ($de > a$) and their products $d^-(d) d^-(e)$:

$$\begin{array}{llll} \{p, pqr\}: qr & \{pq, pq\}: r^2 & \{q, qr\}: p^2r & \{r, pr\}: pq^2 \\ \{pq, pr\}: pqr & \{q, pqr\}: pqr & \{r, qr\}: pqr & \{pq, qr\}: pr^2 \\ \{r, pqr\}: q^2r & \{pr, pr\}: p^2q^2 & \{pq, pqr\}: qr^2 & \{pr, qr\}: p^2qr \\ \{qr, qr\}: p^2r^2 & \{pr, pqr\}: pq^2r & \{qr, pqr\}: pqr^2 & \{pqr, pqr\}: q^2r^2. \end{array}$$

Ordering II ($r > pq$): $1 < p < q < pq < r < pr < qr < pqr$, with

$$d^-(p) = 1, \quad d^-(q) = p, \quad d^-(pq) = q, \quad d^-(r) = pq, \quad d^-(pr) = r, \quad d^-(qr) = pr, \quad d^-(pqr) = qr,$$

and the 16 products:

$$\begin{array}{llll} \{p, pqr\}: qr & \{pq, pr\}: qr & \{q, qr\}: p^2r & \{r, r\}: p^2q^2 \\ \{pq, qr\}: pqr & \{q, pqr\}: pqr & \{r, pr\}: pqr & \{pr, pr\}: r^2 \\ \{pq, pqr\}: q^2r & \{r, qr\}: p^2qr & \{pr, qr\}: pr^2 & \{r, pqr\}: pq^2r \\ \{pr, pqr\}: qr^2 & \{qr, qr\}: p^2r^2 & \{qr, pqr\}: pqr^2 & \{pqr, pqr\}: q^2r^2. \end{array}$$

We read off the minimum. In both orderings the three smallest products are

$$qr \text{ (at } \{p, pqr\}), \quad p^2r \text{ (at } \{q, qr\}), \quad p^2q^2 \text{ (at } \{pr, pr\} \text{ if } r < pq, \text{ or } \{r, r\} \text{ if } r > pq),$$

and no other entry falls below $\min(qr, p^2r, p^2q^2)$. To see this, note every entry other than the two candidates p^2r, p^2q^2 is $\geq qr$. Indeed all entries of the form $c \cdot qr$ or $c \cdot pqr$ with $c \geq 1$ are $\geq qr$; the entry r^2 has $r^2 > qr$ since $r > q$; the entry pr^2 has $pr^2 > qr$ since $pr > q$; and in Ordering I the entry pq^2 (which occurs only there, where $r < pq$) satisfies $pq^2 = q \cdot pq > q \cdot r = qr$ because $pq > r$. Since every entry is either $\geq qr$ or equals one of p^2r, p^2q^2 , the overall minimum is

$$\beta(a) = \min(qr, p^2r, p^2q^2). \quad \square$$

Remark 3. The three candidates give band scales $a^2/qr = p^2qr$, $a^2/(p^2r) = q^2r$, and $a^2/(p^2q^2) = r^2$. In logarithmic exponents $qr = p^{\lambda+\mu}$, $p^2r = p^{2+\mu}$, $p^2q^2 = p^{2+2\lambda}$, so $\beta_3 = qr$ iff $\lambda < 2$ and $\mu < \lambda + 2$; $\beta_3 = p^2r$ iff $\lambda > 2$ and $\mu < 2\lambda$; and $\beta_3 = p^2q^2$ iff $\mu > \max(\lambda + 2, 2\lambda)$. The three surfaces $\lambda = 2$, $\mu = \lambda + 2$, $\mu = 2\lambda$ partition the shape wedge $1 < \lambda < \mu$ into the three regimes, meeting at the triple point $(\lambda, \mu) = (2, 4)$.

3 The upper bound

Proposition 4. *In fixed shape (8), $|X_{pqr}| \ll_{\lambda, \mu} a^2/(\beta_3(a) \log^2 a)$.*

Proof. By the ceiling law (7), the map $m \mapsto (d, e) = (C_a(P^-(m)), C_a(m/P^-(m)))$ sends X_a into the set of ordered divisor pairs with $de > a$, of which there are $O(1)$ (in fact 28). By the refined fiber bound of [3], for a fixed admissible pair with $a/d^-(d) \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\#\{m \in X_a : C_a(P^-(m)) = d, C_a(m/P^-(m)) = e\} \ll \frac{a^2}{d^-(d) d^-(e) \log^2(a/d^-(d))}.$$

In fixed shape every predecessor value is $p^{c+o(1)}$ for a constant $c < 1 + \lambda + \mu$, so $a/d^-(d) = p^{(1+\lambda+\mu)-c+o(1)} \rightarrow \infty$ and $\log(a/d^-(d)) \asymp \log a$, for every pair except those with $d = pqr$ (predecessor qr , so $a/d^- = p$); for those, $\log(a/d^-) = \log p \asymp \log a$ in fixed shape, and the bound reads $\ll a^2/(qr d^-(e) \log^2 p) \ll a^2/(qr \log^2 a)$. Since $d^-(d) d^-(e) \geq \beta(a) = \beta_3(a)$ for every admissible pair (Proposition 2), each of the $O(1)$ fibers is $\ll a^2/(\beta_3(a) \log^2 a)$, and summing gives the bound. \square

4 Survivor families and the lower bound

Each regime is matched by an explicit family. In all three, a member m is a product of two primes chosen so that $am = pqr \cdot m$ is squarefree with five distinct prime factors; the membership $m \in X_a$ is verified by a direct check that every divisor of am is either at most a or exceeds \sqrt{am} , so the window $(a, \sqrt{am}]$ is empty. Throughout we use that $m > a$ implies $\sqrt{am} < m$, so any divisor $\geq m$ already exceeds \sqrt{am} .

Lemma 5 (Family \mathcal{A} , regime $\beta_3 = qr$). *Let t and s be primes with $t < p/2$ and $a/t < s < a$. Then $m = ts \in X_a$.*

Proof. From $t < p$, $a/t = pqr/t > qr$, so $s > qr > r$; thus $t < p < q < r < s$ are five distinct primes, $t, s \notin \{p, q, r\}$, and $am = tpqrs$ is squarefree. Also $m = ts > a$ since $s > a/t$.

Divisors not involving s : these are products of subsets of $\{t, p, q, r\}$. The only one exceeding $a = pqr$ is the full product $tpqr = ta$ (any proper subset replaces some prime by a smaller one or drops it, giving $\leq pqr = a$). For ta we have $ta > m = ts$ because $a > s$ (as $s < a$), so $ta > m > \sqrt{am}$.

Divisors involving s : write such a divisor as hs with $h \mid tpqr$. If $h = 1$ then $hs = s < a$. If $h = t$ then $hs = ts = m > a$, hence $> \sqrt{am}$. If $h > t$ (so h is a divisor of $tpqr$ exceeding t), then $(hs)^2 > am$ iff $h^2s > at$; using $s > a/t$ it suffices that $h^2(a/t) > at$, i.e. $h^2 > t^2$, i.e. $h > t$, which holds. So every divisor hs with $h > t$ exceeds \sqrt{am} .

Hence every divisor of am is $\leq a$ or $> \sqrt{am}$, so $(a, \sqrt{am}]$ is empty and $m \in X_a$. \square

Lemma 6 (Family \mathcal{B} , regime $\beta_3 = p^2r$). *Suppose $\lambda > 2$ (so $q > p^2$). Let x, y be primes with $2p < x < q$ and $a/x < y < qr$. Then $m = xy \in X_a$.*

Proof. From $x < q$, $a/x = pqr/x > pr$, so $y > pr > r$; from $x > 2p$, $a/x < qr/2$, so the interval $(a/x, qr)$ is nonempty. Thus $p < x < q < r < y$ are five distinct primes, $x, y \notin \{p, q, r\}$, $am = pqrxy$ is squarefree, and $m = xy > a$ since $y > a/x$.

Divisors not involving y : these are products of subsets of $\{p, q, r, x\}$. Among the sixteen, only qrx and $pqr x$ exceed $a = pqr$: indeed $qrx > pqr \iff x > p$ (true), $pqr x = ax > a$, while every other subset is $\leq pqr = a$ (e.g. $rx < a \iff x < pq$, true since $x < q$). For qrx , $(qrx)^2 > am = pqrxy \iff qrx > py$, and since $y < qr$ we have $py < pqr < qrx$ (as $x > p$). For $pqr x = ax$, we have $ax > m = xy$ because $a > y$ (indeed $y < qr < a$). Both exceed \sqrt{am} .

Divisors involving y : write such a divisor as hy with $h \mid pqr x$. The only divisors of $pqr x$ less than x are 1 and p ; for these, $y < qr < a$ and $py < pqr = a$ (as $y < qr$), both $\leq a$. Every other divisor h satisfies $h \geq x$, so $hy \geq xy = m > \sqrt{am}$.

Hence every divisor of am is $\leq a$ or $> \sqrt{am}$, and $m \in X_a$. \square

Lemma 7 (Family \mathcal{C} , regime $\beta_3 = p^2q^2$). *Suppose $\mu > 1 + \lambda$ (so $r > pq$ and $\sqrt{a} < r$). Let x, y be primes with $\sqrt{a} < x < y < r$. Then $m = xy \in X_a$.*

Proof. Since $x, y > \sqrt{a}$, $m = xy > a$. Also $\sqrt{a} > q$ (as $\frac{1+\lambda+\mu}{2} > \lambda$, i.e. $1 + \mu > \lambda$, automatic), and $\sqrt{a} > pq$ iff $r > pq$, which holds; so $p < q < x < y < r$ are five distinct primes, $x, y \notin \{p, q, r\}$, and $am = pqrxy$ is squarefree.

Divisors not involving y : products of subsets of $\{p, q, r, x\}$. Among the sixteen, those exceeding $a = pqr$ are exactly $rx, prx, qrx, pqr x$: indeed $rx > pqr \iff x > pq$, true since $x > \sqrt{a} > pq$; and $prx, qrx, pqr x$ are multiples of rx . Every other subset is $\leq a$ (e.g. $qx < a \iff x < pr$, true as $x < r < pr$; $pqx < a \iff x < r$, true). Now $rx > m = xy$ because $r > y$, so $rx > \sqrt{am}$, and $prx, qrx, pqr x$, being multiples of rx , are larger still.

Divisors involving y: write hy with $h \mid pqr x$. The divisors of $pqr x$ less than x are $1, p, q, pq$; for these, $y < r < a$, $py < pr < a$, $qy < qr < a$, and $pqy < pqr = a$ (using $y < r$), all $\leq a$. Every other divisor h satisfies $h \geq x$, so $hy \geq xy = m > \sqrt{am}$.

Hence every divisor of am is $\leq a$ or $> \sqrt{am}$, and $m \in X_a$. \square

Proof of Theorem 1. The upper bound is Proposition 4. For the lower bound we count the family of the active regime.

Regime $\beta_3 = qr$ ($\lambda < 2, \mu < \lambda + 2$). For each prime $t < p/2$ the interval $(a/t, a)$ has length $a(1 - 1/t) \gg a$, so by the prime number theorem it contains $\gg a/\log a$ primes s ; summing over the $\gg p/\log p$ primes $t < p/2$,

$$|\mathcal{A}| \gg \frac{p}{\log p} \cdot \frac{a}{\log a} \asymp \frac{ap}{\log^2 a} = \frac{a^2}{qr \log^2 a},$$

using $ap = p^2 qr = a^2/qr$. By Lemma 5, $\mathcal{A} \subset X_a$.

Regime $\beta_3 = p^2 r$ ($\lambda > 2, \mu < 2\lambda$). For each of the $\gg q/\log q$ primes $x \in (2p, q)$, the interval $(a/x, qr)$ has length $qr - a/x \geq qr/2 \gg qr$, hence $\gg qr/\log a$ primes y ; so

$$|\mathcal{B}| \gg \frac{q}{\log q} \cdot \frac{qr}{\log a} \asymp \frac{q^2 r}{\log^2 a} = \frac{a^2}{p^2 r \log^2 a}.$$

By Lemma 6, $\mathcal{B} \subset X_a$.

Regime $\beta_3 = p^2 q^2$ ($\mu > \max(\lambda + 2, 2\lambda)$). Here $\sqrt{a} = r^\theta$ with $\theta = \frac{1+\lambda+\mu}{2\mu} < 1$, so (\sqrt{a}, r) contains $\gg r/\log r \asymp r/\log a$ primes; choosing two of them,

$$|\mathcal{C}| \gg \left(\frac{r}{\log a}\right)^2 = \frac{r^2}{\log^2 a} = \frac{a^2}{p^2 q^2 \log^2 a}.$$

By Lemma 7, $\mathcal{C} \subset X_a$.

In each regime the lower bound matches Proposition 4, proving the theorem. \square

5 The general squarefree conjecture

Theorem 1 and the companion notes establish, for squarefree a with $\omega(a) \leq 3$, that $|X_a| \asymp a^2/(\beta(a) \log^2 a)$ with $\beta(a)$ the band invariant (6). The proofs share a feature worth isolating. The exact count of X_a is a sum over divisor-pair fibers, and for $\omega(a) \geq 3$ two distinct pairs play distinct roles. The fiber that holds the most members tends to be the one attached to the smallest prime—for $a = pqr$ it is the pair (pqr, p) , a rough-number (Buchstab) count with no clean two-prime description—yet its predecessor product need not be the extremal one: across the three regimes the extremal pair realizing β_3 is (p, pqr) , (q, qr) , or (r, r) respectively, generally distinct from the largest fiber. The lower bound reaches the band scale through a clean two-prime family attached to the *extremal* pair (here $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}$), while the populous rough fiber contributes at most the same order and is absorbed into \asymp . Thus, despite the multi-sector structure, the order is set by the single extremal predecessor product $\beta(a)$, not by which fiber is largest. This suggests:

Conjecture 8. *For squarefree $a = p_1 \cdots p_k$ with $p_1 < \cdots < p_k$, in fixed logarithmic shape and away from boundary transitions,*

$$|X_a| \asymp \frac{a^2}{\beta(a) \log^2 a}, \quad \beta(a) = \min\{d^-(d) d^-(e) : d, e \mid a, de > a\}.$$

For $k = 1$, $\beta = 1$ and this is (3); for $k = 2$, $\beta = \min(q, p^2)$, (5); for $k = 3$, $\beta = \min(qr, p^2r, p^2q^2)$, Theorem 1. The conjecture asserts that the same single-extremal-pair law persists for all k : the upper bound is the divisor-pair majorant of [3] (always valid), so the content is the existence, for every squarefree a , of a clean survivor family reaching the scale $a^2/(\beta(a) \log^2 a)$.

Remark 9. Direct computation supports the conjecture at $\omega(a) = 4$. For squarefree a with four prime factors and a^2 within reach, the ratio $|X_a|/(a^2/\beta(a) \log^2 a)$ stays bounded (of the same magnitude, 4 to 6, as the verified $\omega(a) \leq 3$ cases at comparable a), and the measured exponent $\log |X_a|/\log a$ tracks the band exponent $2 - \log_a \beta(a)$. The data show no break in the law at $\omega(a) = 4$, the first place a clean family could fail to reach the extremal pair. Proving the conjecture in general requires constructing such a family uniformly in k and the shape; the present three families indicate the construction is governed by which predecessor product is extremal, but a uniform statement remains open.

References

- [1] E. Fodge, *The size of the central-divisor exception set for prime layers*. (companion note; Zenodo DOI to be inserted).
- [2] E. Fodge, *The central-divisor exception set for prime-power layers: a multiplicity-graded size exponent*. (companion note; Zenodo DOI to be inserted).
- [3] E. Fodge, *A divisor-ceiling law for central-divisor exception sets*. (companion note; Zenodo DOI to be inserted).
- [4] K. Ford, *The distribution of integers with a divisor in a given interval*, Ann. of Math. **168** (2008), 367–433.